

***ASTRONOMIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA AXBOROT
TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI***

Ilmiy rahbar: Sayfullayeva Gulhayo Ixtiyor qizi-

Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti dotsenti

Norqulova Madina Hamza qizi-

Navoiy davlat pedagogika instituti talabasi

Kalit so'zlar: axborot, texnologiya, astronomiya, zamonaviy, electron, intellect

Annotatsiya: Jahonning rivojlangan mamlakatlarida astronomiya fanini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarni (vebinar, onlayn, blended learning, flipped classroom) va gipermatnli interaktiv dasturiy vositalardan, virtual ta'lim texnologiyalari, sun'iy intellekt tizimlari, axborot ta'lim muhitlarini o'zaro integratsiyalash asosida o'qitish masalalariga doir tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda.

Ta'lim oluvchilarning astronomiya sohasida okeanlar, materiklar, astronomik o'lkalar, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy astronomiya, zamonaviy ekologik muammolar, dunyo aholisi, umumiy yer tuzilishiga oid ijodiy qobiliyati, mantiqiy, kreativ fikrlashini oshirish, kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish va ta'lim jarayonini tizimlashtirishning nazariy-metodologik hamda uslubiy asoslarini takomillashtirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Dunyo miqyosida ta'lim tizimini barqaror taraqqiyot tendensiyalariga moslashtirish sharoitida astronomiya ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonini muammoli o'qitish texnologiyalari negizida gipermedia texnologiyalaridan, axborot ta'lim muhitlaridan foydalanishning strategiyalari va mexanizmlarini zamonaviy rivojlanish tamoyillari asosida takomillashtirishda LMS tizimlarini hamda vebga mo'ljallangan zamonaviy didaktik pedagogik dasturiy vositalarni tadbiq etish asosida ta'lim oluvchilarning kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishga qaratilgan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari olib borilmoqda. Tadqiqot natijalari astronomiya fanlarini o'qitishning metodologik, tizimli-faoliyat va shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlarini hamda o'quvchi-talabalarning mustaqil o'quv faoliyatida kreativ va kognitiv fikrlashini rivojlantirishga doir ilmiy-nazariy ishlanmalar samaradorligini oshirish dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim muassasalarida astronomiya fanlaridan o'quvchi-talabalarning ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonini samarali tashkil etishning zamonaviy yondashuvlarini ishlab chiqish bilan pedagog kadrlarni tayyorlashda didaktik raqamli o'quv vositalari va ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarni o'zaro integratsiyasini ta'minlash orqali o'qitishning innovatsion shakllari va usullarini joriy etish imkoniyatlari

yaratilmoqda. O'z navbatida oliy ta'lim muassasalarida astronomiya fanlarini o'qitishda axborot ta'lim muhitlaridan foydalanish metodikasini takomillashtirish zarurati paydo bo'lmoqda.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

M Muhabbat, B Aziza, GI Sayfullayeva **Elements Of The Credit-Module System In Higher Education In The Republic Of Uzbekistan** Web Of Scientists And Scholars: Journal Of Multidisciplinary Research 1 (8 ...

M Muhabbat, B Aziza, GI Sayfullayeva **OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM** Web Of Humanities: Journal Of Social Science And Humanitarian Research 1 (8 ...

Сабирова, Н. Э. (2021). ИЗ ИСТОРИИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИСКУССТВА ХАЛФА ХОРЕЗМА. In АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТЮРКОЛОГИИ: РОССИЯ И ТЮРКО-МУСУЛЬМАНСКИЙ МИР (pp. 387-390).

M Muhabbat, B Aziza, GI Sayfullayeva **FINAL CONTROL WORK DISTANT. TSUL. UZ DOWNLOAD INSTRUCTION TO THE DISTANCE LEARNING PLATFORM** Web Of Teachers: Inderscience Research 1 (8), 82-86

M Muhabbat, B Aziza, GI Sayfullayeva **THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION** Web Of Technology: Multidimensional Research Journal 1 (8), 9-11

Сабирова, Н. Э. (2014). Фольклор и его значение в воспитании детей. In Актуальные вопросы современной науки (pp. 139-142).

M Muhabbat, B Aziza, GI Sayfullayeva **ADVANTAGES OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM IN EDUCATION** Web Of Discoveries: Journal Of Analysis And Inventions 1 (8), 9-13

Сабирова, Н. Э. (2018). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СИМВОЛОВ ОБРЯДОВЫХ ПЕСЕН, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ДРЕВНИМИ КУЛЬТАМИ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION (pp. 73-74).

R Nilufar, GI Sayfullayeva **Principles Of The Credit-Module System** Diversity Research: Journal Of Analysis And Trends 1 (8), 49-52

AM Bozorova **OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA ASTRONOMIYA
KURSIDAN MASHG'ULOTLARNI O'QITISHDA VA TALABA
KOMPETENTLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN
INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARINI JORIY ...Journal Of Science-
Innovative Research In Uzbekistan 1 (8), 6-11**

SH Rozikulovich, S Gulhayo **METHODOLOGY FOR FINDING THE TOPIC
OF THE EARTH IN DISTANCE EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF AN
INTEGRATIVE APPROACH Journal Of Academic Research And Trends In
Educational Sciences 1 (10), 21-33 2022**

Sabirova Nasiba Ergashevna. (2023). **THE GENESIS OF BAKHSH
PERFORMANCE IN THE KHOREZM REGION. Spectrum Journal of Innovation,
Reforms and Development, 14, 134–138. Retrieved from
<https://sjird.journalspark.org/index.php/sjird/article/view/616>**

GI Sayfullayeva, HR Shodiyev **KREDIT MODUL TIZIMIDA FANLARNI
INTEGRATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA O 'QITISHNING AFZALLIKLARI**